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Efficient Lazy Theta* Path Planning over a Sparse Grid to Explore Large 3D Volumes with a Multirotor UAV

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Abstract: Exploring large, unknown and unstructured environments is challenging for UAVs, but they are valuable tools to inspect large structures safely and efficiently. The Lazy Theta* path planning algorithm is revisited and adapted to generate paths fast enough to be used in real-time and outdoors in large 3D scenarios. In real unknown scenarios, a given minimum safety distance to the nearest obstacle or unknown space should be observed, increasing the associated obstacle detection queries and creating a bottleneck in the path planning algorithm. We have reduced the dimension of the problem by considering geometrical properties in order to speed up these computations. On the other hand, we have also applied a non-regular grid representation of the world to increase the performance of the path planning algorithm. In particular, a sparse resolution grid in the form of an octree is used, organizing the measurements spatially, merging voxels when they are of the same state. Additionally, the number of neighbors is trimmed to match the sparse tree in order to reduce the number of obstacle detection queries. The development methodology adopted was Test Driven Development (TDD) and the outcome was evaluated in real outdoors flights with a multirotor UAV. In the results, the performance shows over ninety percent decrease in overall path generation computation time. Furthermore, our approach scales well with the safety distance increases.

Keywords: Path planning; UAV; Autonomous Exploration; Sparse Grids; Lazy Theta*

1. Introduction

The role of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) as tools in human activities only now begins to unfold. Many multirotor UAV platforms are now commercially available. Their applicability is bounded chiefly by creativity and novelty. Examples of tasks aided by UAVs are package transportation [1,2], industrial inspection [3–8], scene reconstruction [9–11], and environmental monitoring [12–14]. These applications, closer to the daily life, take place outside controlled environments. To fully exploit the potential of UAVs, a key challenge is to plan paths and create maps in complex, unstructured environments. Resources aboard UAVs are scarce. Complex algorithms require processing power. Weight constraints, limit available range of usable processors. The resources must be shared among all tasks. Despite these constraints, exploration has recently been extended to three-dimensional domains. Examples are sewer exploration [5], bridge inspection [4], and forest exploration [15].

Autonomous exploration can be formulated as an active learning problem. It is a problem that incorporates simultaneous localization, mapping, and planning [16]. Rapid technological developments in aerial robotics and robotic sensors have motivated significant research in motion planning, as discussed in the survey of Goerzen et al. [17]. This paper focuses on the planning task in time-invariant, static and near-static environments. These algorithms avoid the need for complex, time-consuming manual mission planning on densely occupied space.

In this research, design choices and solutions are guided by the use case targeted: a rotary wing UAV whose task is the autonomous exploration of a large, unknown, and unstructured environment. Examples of such scenarios include search and rescue, archaeological structures, and inspection of industrial facilities.

34 As noted by Goerzen et al. [17], the characteristics of the particular application are key in determining how
35 to solve the motion planning problem. In an exploration scenario, the unexplored space can contain obstacles.
36 To keep the UAV safely inside the known free space and avoid obstacles, the planner conservatively treats the
37 unknown space as an obstacle. Another characteristic of the use case is that the map is constructed during
38 exploration. As a result each path request evolves over different versions of the map, the benefits of precalculated
39 distances cannot be fully exploited. Because the UAV is omnidirectional, its orientation is not part of the
40 configuration space. Due to the large dimensions of the space to be explored, the computation time must scale
41 well with the length of the generated path. To be a self-contained, flexible tool, the planner must be real-time
42 and onboard. As a result, the UAV can operate under severe restrictions of ground station connectivity and
43 throughput rate. Tools either for industrial or commercial use must provide guarantees about the results and
44 need to be certified. Repeatability is a vital characteristic. These traits are straightforward to achieve with
45 deterministic algorithms. However, their major drawback is the tendency to employ more calculations, thereby
46 limiting computational efficiency.

47 This research improves the efficiency of the implementation of Lazy Theta* previously presented in [7],
48 an algorithm that has been applied successfully in competitions with multirotor UAVs [18] and fulfills the
49 requirements mentioned above. For realistic obstacle avoidance, the concept of a flight corridor was introduced
50 in order to detect obstacles that are around the trajectory. The dimensions of the flight corridor reflect the
51 volume of the UAV and its operational restrictions, including localization uncertainty, trajectory following error,
52 mapping errors, etc. However, this shift introduces a significant bottleneck. Obstacle avoidance now uses at least
53 ninety-five percent of the computational time as shown later. A sparse resolution grid in the form of an octree is
54 used to represent the world, organizing the measurements spatially, merging voxels when they are of the same
55 state. Furthermore, this representation is well suited to store information about large scenarios as it requires little
56 memory.

57 The main contributions of the paper are (1) presenting an Any Angle path planning algorithm that generates
58 three-dimensional paths with an obstacle-free flight corridor around the trajectory, implemented over sparse
59 grids; (2) introducing a two-phased approach to obstacle detection that qualifies Lazy Theta* for real-time,
60 onboard usage as both a local and global planner; (3) refine neighborhood generation by taking into account the
61 multi-resolution nature of the octree; (4) adoption of the methodology Test Driven Development (TDD) paired
62 with smart monkey testing.

63 The algorithm can generate paths as a local planner because the resolution of the octomap is fine enough to
64 navigate around the obstacle. The paths created can be used directly by the autopilot. The planner is also able to
65 generate paths as a global planner because it scales well to long paths. The path can go up to a hundred times the
66 size of the resolution, overcoming local minima.

67 The implementation of Lazy Theta* as well as the maps used in testing are open sourced and available
68 at https://github.com/margaridaCF/FlyingOctomap_code. Videos illustrating the results can be found at <https://sites.google.com/view/lazythetastaronline/videos>.

70 In section 2 is an overview of the state of the art. The contributions are analyzed in depth in section 3. The
71 proposed method is described in section 4 and tested in experimental scenarios in section 5. Finally, the main
72 conclusions are drawn in section 6.

73 2. Related Work

74 This section reviews the state-of-the-art in path planning, mentioning autonomous exploration. In particular,
75 the following discussion of prior studies focuses on collision avoidance and scalability, as these are some of the
76 critical features of the proposed algorithm.

77 In any robot navigation scenario, a crucial task is to, given a set of global destination waypoints,
78 plan collision-free paths that satisfy motion constraints. Yang et al. [19] presents a thorough survey of the
79 state-of-the-art in three-dimensional motion planning. Within their taxonomy, algorithms are distinguished as
80 being (i) deterministic or (ii) non-deterministic. Unlike deterministic methods, non-deterministic strategies are
81 not guaranteed to produce the same outputs over multiple runs. As such, deterministic algorithms naturally
82 satisfy any repeatability requirements, which commonly arise in industrial inspection scenarios.

83 Non-deterministic, sampling-based algorithms apply continuous path planning to high-dimensional spaces.
84 Some examples include Rapidly-Exploring Random Trees (RRTs) [20,21] and the Probabilistic Road Map
85 (PRM) [22]. These approaches leverage uniform sampling to grow a connectivity structure, e.g., a tree or graph,
86 towards unexplored areas of the problem instance. More recent studies in this field [4,23,24] propose variations of
87 RRTs to improve the optimality and computational speed of sampling-based algorithms. For UAVs in particular,
88 Oleynikova et al. [25] and Lin and Saripalli [26] present probabilistic approaches to generate collision-free
89 trajectories in cluttered environments. In inspection scenarios, various non-deterministic planners have emerged
90 to sample efficiently promising viewpoint configurations in continuous space. Typically, these methods either
91 only consider greedy next-best views [4] or incorporate a non-myopic look-ahead to escape local minima [11].
92 Song and Jo [27] employ a two-step strategy based on primal and dual sampling to generate paths for constructing
93 accurate three-dimensional models of an unknown environment. The works Bircher et al. [4], Papachristos et al.
94 [5], and Papachristos et al. [6] adopt a receding horizon planning strategy, sampling possible future configurations
95 in a geometric random tree. More recently, Witting et al. [28] presented a polynomial trajectory-based planner
96 which exploits a history graph to direct the growth of an RRT towards unexplored regions of a target environment.
97 Recent work in this field by Papachristos et al. [6], and Francis et al. [29] has tackled incorporating the UAV's
98 pose uncertainty into the planning objective for improved map quality.

99 In a similar problem set-up, Heng et al. [9] tackle visual exploration and coverage by performing
100 optimization in the UAV state space. The search is done in four dimensions (position and orientation) accelerating
101 the computation by relying on a precomputation of the swath of the motion and the sensor range shape. This
102 approach delivers dynamically feasible plans and demonstrates scalability to office-size environments. Whereas
103 stochastic approaches enable efficient exploration of large volumes, they cannot deliver repeatable results. The
104 scale of the scenarios targeted in these studies varies widely. In simulated environments, e.g., [4,9,28], the
105 workspace volumes span 1.000 – 10.000 m³, whereas in experimental settings, e.g., [5,28], they are constrained
106 to 100 – 200 m³. In contrast, the proposed approach was applied in significantly larger simulated and real
107 environments, on the orders of 520.000 m³ and 11.000 m³, respectively.

108 Visibility graphs are another option for world representation. In general, the cost of building a fully
109 connected graph presents a good trade-off when the same graph is queried multiple times. For example, Scholer
110 et al. [30] construct a three-dimensional visibility graph for UAVs, composed of one obstacle, and two supporting
111 graphs. The approach relies on a fully known environment. Consequently, the graph is built once, with the
112 high build cost restricted to initialization. This requirement is incompatible with dynamic maps that are built in
113 real-time during a mission.

114 To enable consistent, repeatable results in large-scale environments, the strategy of this research opts for
115 a deterministic, complete method to navigate to the map's frontiers. One algorithm with this characteristics is
116 A* [31], and it also guarantees to find the best path. Radmanesh et al. [32] compare various path planners in
117 three different scenarios. Among the deterministic path planning algorithms without associated error, A* has the
118 smallest computation time. However, one major drawback is that paths are formed by the edges of a discrete grid.
119 As such, their results do not necessarily correspond to shortest paths in continuous space. Often the paths have
120 sharp edges that are difficult to track with practical controllers. The Any-Angle family of algorithms addresses
121 this issue by generating paths outside the grid's edges. The Field D* algorithm [33] uses interpolation to choose
122 in what point of the grid's edge to cross to the next voxel. It has been used in two dimensions for the Mars rovers
123 Spirit, Opportunity, and Curiosity. In [34] a simulated micro-UAV vehicle goes from start to goal using an AD*
124 search algorithm for replanning. The underlying world representation is a three-dimensional occupancy grid that
125 is sampled where the samples are arranged as a multi-dimensional lattice.

126 Another Any-Angle algorithm is Theta* [35]. Here the path is found by evaluating the connection not only
127 between neighbors but also between the neighbor of a candidate and its previous waypoint. Theta* is less suited
128 for real-time constraints because of the high number of line-of-sight checks it performs [36]. The Lazy Theta*
129 extension was presented by Nash et al. [36] and has been extensively used for two-dimensional paths generated
130 over regular grids of various shapes [37–39]. This extension reduces the number of line-of-sight checks, which is
131 a crucial aspect in alleviating the effect of the obstacle detection bottleneck. Some work has been done applying
132 Lazy Theta* to three dimensions but always over regular grids. One example is [40], although video games

133 are the primary use case it can be used to any continuous terrain. Garcia *et al.* [41] also applies Lazy Theta*
134 for three-dimensional path planning for UAVs navigating in hazardous weather conditions. In this work are
135 quantitatively compared A*, Theta* and Lazy Theta*. The computation time is similar, the cost is lower for
136 Lazy Theta* as well as the number of line of sight checks performed. However, the time constraints only make
137 Lazy Theta* suitable to act as a global planner. Faria *et al.* [7] applies Lazy Theta* to three dimensions using
138 a sparse tree. In this type of structure, voxels with the same state are merged. The spatial clustering enables
139 the spatial analysis to be done in a computationally efficient manner because each time a voxel is examined the
140 corresponding volume is analyzed at once. Moreover, this permits scaling path generation to larger scenarios,
141 e.g., a building or oil rig.

142 3. Increasing the efficiency of Lazy Theta* for Exploration

143 In the adopted setup, the information from the world comes from a distance sensor mounted on the UAV.
144 First, the distance measurements form a point cloud that translates the space around the robot. Then the point
145 clouds are combined in the internal representation of the world, the octree. Finally, the octree merges voxels of
146 the same value into larger voxels. However, the Lazy Theta* path planner generates a path over a graph. Let the
147 voxel's centers in the trees be the nodes of the graph, and the connections between neighbors be the edges.

148 Sparse trees present an opportunity to simplify the regular grid, adjusting the resolution to the terrain
149 configuration. Octrees are one way to represent sparse grids, they are trees with a maximum of eight children
150 and, as a result, have a flatter hierarchy than binary trees making them faster to traverse. Both because of the
151 focus on low memory requirements and on information organization, the octree implementation used for world
152 representation is the octomap framework [42,43]. In the octomap implementation, information is added not only
153 for detected occupied locations but also for the free space. The free space is extrapolated from the location of the
154 sensor and of the obstacle. Furthermore, the spatial clustering more efficient calculations as each time a voxel is
155 examined, the corresponding volume is analyzed at once.

156 The major benefits of Lazy Theta* add to the potential of the sparse tree. The any-angle property of
157 the resulting path and the reduced amount of obstacle detection checks combined, address the computational
158 restrictions imposed by the onboard and real-time requirements. The paths generated are smooth enough to
159 dispense post-processing algorithms. In addition, the reduced number of calculations enable the planner to be
160 used both at the local and the global level.

161 This work maintains the guarantees given in the original Lazy Theta* algorithm [36]. Excluding time
162 restrictions, it is a complete, deterministic algorithm.

163 3.1. Flight Corridor

164 In Nash *et al.* [36] is presented the Lazy Theta* path planning algorithm, later in Faria *et al.* [7] it is
165 implemented over an octree. However, in [7] the UAV is treated as a single point. Both the UAV's volume and
166 the maximum distance to obstacles need to be taken into account to ensure reliable obstacle avoidance. The
167 safety margin provides a failsafe from the different sources of error: the combined sensor error, the quantization
168 error, and the trajectory tracking error. Additionally, to be able to fly, allowances must be made to include the
169 human safety pilot's reaction time in the loop.

170 However, an obstacle detection bottleneck arises when switching from a point vehicle type of problem (as
171 defined in [17]) into checking the volume of the flight corridor, as shown later. A significant contribution of this
172 work is to include realistic obstacle avoidance while keeping the runtime appropriate for real-time and onboard
173 use.

174 3.2. Sparse neighbors

175 The motivation behind selecting a multi-resolution octree grid as the world representation is to merge voxels
176 with an equal state (either free, occupied or unknown). One consequence of this choice is the variable number of
177 neighbors. As the number of merged voxels increases, the number of neighbors increases exponentially. At the
178 base of the tree resolution, a voxel with the size of the resolution has six neighbors. Going up three levels, a voxel
179 that is only four times the size of the map's resolution can already have 384 neighbors. At the top of the tree, at

180 the sixteenth level, a voxel can have 6.442.450.944 neighbors. The total number of neighbors depends on the
 181 configuration of the space. However, this variability in voxel size can also be used to speed up the calculations as
 182 all the neighbors with the same state are analyzed at the same time.

183 In [7], the neighbors are generated always assuming maximum resolution neighborhood. While this may
 184 occur, it is an extreme edge case, especially for larger voxels. An edge case is a case where among all the input
 185 variables one occurs at an extreme (maximum or minimum), even though within limits. The neighbors must be
 186 calculated in a flexible way to adapt to their variable size and exploit the multi-resolution structure of the tree.
 187 Fewer neighbors will lead to fewer obstacle checks, hence reducing the time needed for these verifications.

188 This optimization raises again the problem of voxel identification discussed in [7]. The two pieces of
 189 information associated with a voxel (its coordinates and its key) are not unique. Coordinates overlap as each
 190 leaf voxel is enclosed in larger parents and the key is unique only within the tree level. Fortunately, the two
 191 characteristics are unique when combined: the coordinates of the center of the leaf voxel and the voxel's size.
 192 Combining characteristics that are not unique individually creates a composite key, a common technique in
 193 relational databases.

194 3.3. Efficient Geometric Obstacle Detection

195 In [7], the UAV is abstracted as a point. Nevertheless, a maximum safety margin to an obstacle must be
 196 observed all around the vehicle. In this work, the volume around the trajectory that must be free to fly is referred
 197 to as the flight corridor. The original pseudo-code of Lazy Theta* [36] is not affected by the inclusion of this
 198 concept. What must change is how visibility is calculated both from a node to its neighbors¹ and between the
 199 two nodes start and end². For this task, the resolution of the map is considered as the discretization step within
 200 the flight corridor.

201 Let ${}^G S = (x_S, y_S, z_S)$ be the start position and ${}^G E = (x_E, y_E, z_E)$ the end position. Furthermore, let us define
 202 \mathbf{d} as the vector that goes from the start position to the end position, $(x_E - x_S, y_E - y_S, z_E - z_S) = (d_1, d_2, d_3)$.
 203 Craig's notation in [44] is adopted in this paper.

204 Two approaches to obstacle detection are considered in this work. First, in subsection 3.3.1, the
 205 three-dimensional discretization is summarized. Secondly, in subsection 3.3.2, is described the two-dimensional
 206 discretization.

207 3.3.1. Three-Dimensional Discretization

208 One option for obstacle checking within the flight corridor is to segment the space in all three axis x, y, and
 209 z. The discretization step matches the resolution of the octomap to guarantee that all voxels between the start and
 210 end positions are covered. This discretization creates a rectangular corridor, the width of the corridor is twice
 211 that of the safety margin. In the center of the corridor is \mathbf{d} , the length of the corridor is $|\mathbf{d}|$. The line segments
 212 obtained with the discretization have the direction of \mathbf{d} and are independent of the alignment of the octomap.

213 3.3.2. Geometrical Two-Dimensional Discretization

The flight corridor can also be represented as a cylinder with the \mathbf{d} vector in the center and height $|\mathbf{d}|$. The
 discs in each end can be expressed as circles. Where the circle around ${}^G S$ is

$${}^G C_S = \begin{cases} (x - x_S)^2 + (y - y_S)^2 + (z - z_S)^2 = r^2 \\ d_1(x - x_S) + d_2(y - y_S) + d_3(z - z_S) = 0 \end{cases}$$

¹ Lazy Theta* pseudocode in [36] lines 12, 37 and 38.

² Lazy Theta* pseudocode in [36] line 35.

Figure 1. Ray traces used in the geometrical approach. The cylindrical shape with the hemisphere around the goal can be identified in both images. (a) Visualization of the flight corridor with the grid illustrating the space discretization resolution. (b) Simulation example in which red rays have collided with obstacles but green rays are in free space.

and ${}^G C_E$ is analogous around ${}^G E$. Their radius is half the width of the flight corridor. Around the end position, the free space must also be verified forwards, forming the hemisphere at the end of the cylinder ${}^G H_E$

$${}^G H_E = \begin{cases} (x - x_E)^2 + (y - y_E)^2 + (z - z_E)^2 = r^2, \\ d_1(x - x_E) + d_2(y - y_E) + d_3(z - z_E) \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

214 The flight corridor is the union of the cylinder and the hemisphere.

215 As only the bases of the cylinder are discretized, only the y and z axis need to be discretized reducing the
216 number of discretized dimensions. The rays are cast from the base that contains the start position, ${}^G C_S$, to the
217 hemisphere around the endpoint, ${}^G H_E$. Figure 1 shows this concept graphically both geometrically and with a
218 simulated example.

219 Let us define r as half the flight corridor width, Δ is the map resolution and the maximum, \max , is equal to
220 $2r/\Delta$. Then we find the two sets of points that correspond to ${}^G C_S$ and ${}^G H_E$. We start by generating C_S and H_E in
221 local frames, around the zero as

222 ${}^L C_{Si,j} = (0 \quad y_{i,j} \quad z_{i,j})^T$, ${}^L H_{Ei,j} = (\sqrt{r^2 - y_{i,j}^2 - z_{i,j}^2} \quad y_{i,j} \quad z_{i,j})^T$, $\forall i, j \in [0, \max] \cap \mathbb{Z}$, where $y_{i,j} =$
223 $i\Delta - r$ and $z_{i,j} = j\Delta - r$. The points are included in the set only if they fulfill the condition $y_{i,j}^2 + z_{i,j}^2 \leq r^2$.
224 The number of points around the start ${}^L C_{Si,j}$ and the end ${}^L H_{Ei,j}$, as well as their relative position, can be calculated
225 only once at the beginning. These sets of points will be referenced here as the offsets.

226 During the path generation, when a start-end pair is known, the transformation of these sets of points from
227 the local frames to the global frame is composed by a rotation and a translation. The rotation is the same for both
228 start and end and is computed as it is shown in Algorithm 1. The rotation aligns the circle and the hemisphere to
229 be orthogonal to \mathbf{d} . The translations, center the sets of points in the global frame as

$$\begin{bmatrix} {}^G C_S \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} {}^L R & | & {}^G C_S \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & | & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} {}^L C_S \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} {}^G H_E \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} {}^L R & | & {}^G E \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & | & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} {}^L H_E \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

230 In this application, the more convenient shapes around each base of the cylinder are a circle and a convex
231 semi-sphere. However, this approach can be used with any shape.

Algorithm 1 Generate a rotation matrix to transform from the local coordinate frame into the global coordinate frame. The z-axis is used to calculate a vector orthogonal to \mathbf{d} . The exception is to avoid precision issues with the cross-product due to collinearity. The final axis is orthogonal to both directions and the previously-found axis. The vector \hat{Z}_L is always pointing as vertical as possible. The algorithm is applied to each set of start and end positions as the rotation is the same for both local frames.

Input: \mathbf{d}

Output: ${}^L_G R$

$$1: \hat{X}_L = \frac{\mathbf{d}}{\|\mathbf{d}\|}$$

2: **if** $\hat{X}_L \cdot \hat{Z}_G \leq 0.9$ **then**

$$3: \hat{Y}_L = \frac{\hat{Z}_G \times \hat{X}_L}{\|\hat{Z}_G \times \hat{X}_L\|}$$

4: **else**

$$5: \hat{Y}_L = \frac{\hat{X}_L \times \hat{X}_G}{\|\hat{X}_L \times \hat{X}_G\|}$$

6: **end if**

$$7: \hat{Z}_L = \hat{X}_L \times \hat{Y}_L$$

$$8: {}^L_G R = \{\hat{X}_L, \hat{Y}_L, \hat{Z}_L\}$$

9: **return** ${}^L_G R$

232 4. Development Methodology

233 This paper builds upon the work presented in the article [7], which describes the implementation of Lazy
 234 Theta* using octomap as the world representation. The goal is to enable the generation of paths in an amount
 235 of time compatible with real-time requirements. A preliminary run of the original implementation in outdoor
 236 flights revealed that obstacle avoidance is the major computational bottleneck, as is shown later. The reduction
 237 of obstacle detection calculations was twofold. Firstly, due to the multi-resolution nature of the map, the large
 238 voxels generate many regular grid neighbors. Moreover, by discretizing in two dimensions instead of three the
 239 number of rays required to check a flight corridor is reduced. In order to realistically evaluate the incremental
 240 changes of the implementation, different techniques from software engineering were employed as described in
 241 section 4.1.

242 The change in computational time is less evident in the context of path generation because obstacle detection
 243 stops as soon as an obstacle is found. To validate the impact of the two discretization approaches on computational
 244 time, the worst-case scenario was selected as the benchmark. Each time the corridor is searched, all rays are cast
 245 regardless of whether an obstacle is found.

246 The flight corridor provides a failsafe from different sources of error: (1) the combined sensor error (Inertial
 247 measurement unit - IMU, Global Navigation Satellite System - GNSS, Light Detection and Ranging - LIDAR),
 248 (2) the quantization error, percentage of voxel occupied by the obstacle, and (3) the trajectory tracking error
 249 resulting both from the controller and from external perturbations, such as wind gusts. In a practical outdoors
 250 setting, allowances must be made to include the safety pilot in the loop. The flight corridor must cater for the
 251 reaction time of the safety pilot. According to Loffi et al. [45], the minimal time to identify and react to another
 252 UAV in a collision trajectory is twelve seconds and a half. Identifying a collision trajectory with a static object is
 253 a considerably faster task. However, the study informs on how to narrow down the values for the flight corridor.

254 4.1. Software Engineering Considerations

255 To verify that the implementation achieves the intended results under all possible conditions is a non-trivial
 256 task. However, it is crucial to ensure that changes in the code still produce previously verified behaviors. This
 257 challenge is also faced in the area of software development and can be addressed with tools from that field.

258 In the development, testing, and data collection procedures several concepts from the software engineering
 259 field were employed. Different setups or development environments were successively applied to expose the

260 program to the computational time restrictions incrementally. In order to create stable, well-tested code, the
 261 development was done in tandem with a suite of tests that verifies each required behavior. Finally, the data
 262 collection was automated whenever possible to generate thousands of paths.

263 The idea of bringing tools and paradigms from software engineering into robotics is more and more common.
 264 One example is the European project RobMoSys [46] that uses flexible general-purpose modeling of systems
 265 with the Unified Modeling Language as a reference. Another example is the use of the continuous integration
 266 tool of software developments docker adopted in the ROS build farms, robotics companies [47] and even the
 267 ROS-Industrial Consortia [48].

268 4.1.1. Development Environments and Data

269 The code was developed mimicking the environments used in Continuous Integration practises to deliver
 270 software. Three different environments or setups were used: development or Dev, Hardware in the Loop (HitL)
 271 and Flight. Each environment is defined by the processor and type of data used for the tests. They are progressed
 272 through in this order to face increasingly realistic and restrictive conditions, as can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Listing of three development environments. Environments are defined by processor choice, the type of map used, and the data collection location.

Order	Development Environment	Type of map	Processors	Data collection
1	Dev	Synthetic and experimental snapshots	Intel® Core™ i7	-
2	HitL	Synthetic and experimental snapshots	Intel® Atom™ x5	Yes
3	Flight	Continuously generated	Intel® Atom™ x5	Yes

273 Table 1 describes the order each environment is progressed through as well as the corresponding setup. In
 274 both environments where data collection takes place (HitL and Flight), the processor used to generate a path is
 275 the same. Dev, the first environment, is reserved for a faster prototyping phase.

276 The distance sensor onboard is a two-dimensional laser. The maps are classified into three types: synthetic,
 277 experimental snapshots, and continuously generated. Synthetic refers to maps produced by integrating laser
 278 readings generated by the simulator. An experimental snapshot is a map created during a flight that corresponds
 279 to the state of the map at a particular moment. Finally, the continuously generated map changes throughout the
 280 runtime of the algorithm as the laser readings are continually integrated. This last environment closer mimics the
 281 exploration use case where the map is continuously generated in an unknown environment. The generation of
 282 each type of map is detailed in section 5.1.

283 4.1.2. Test Driven Development

284 Testing is a crucial aspect in all software development, nevertheless in the case of the TTD methodology it
 285 is particularly important since for each requirement, a failing test is created, then the code is refined until that
 286 test no longer fails. To achieve stable code throughout the development process, the behavior of the methods is
 287 captured in tests that warn when the correct values are not calculated. In software engineering terminology they
 288 are called unit tests. Several tools exist to automate the testing process. The ROS integration of Google's C++
 289 unit testing framework gtest [49] is the tool selected for automated unit testing. In tests that address the path
 290 generation as a whole (instead of the smaller functions comprising it) the input consists of five variables: the
 291 map, the starting coordinates, the goal coordinates, the size of the flight corridor, and the maximum amount of
 292 seconds the path planner has to find a solution.

293 Smart monkey testing³ is adopted to identify extreme input combinations independently of the bias of the
 294 developer. The planner is integrated into an exploration architecture to generate a flight plan for each new goal
 295 location. The autonomous exploration process inspects a large scenario for two hours to collect laser data. As

³ In Software Testing terminology, monkey testing refers to testing with random input. Smart monkey testing is a more specific form of testing where knowledge of the software is embedded into the test as well the capacity to report found problems or bugs.

296 the world representation is built during exploration, the path planner is tested on different versions of the map.
297 Consequently, the algorithm is applied to many combinations of the input variables although always in a synthetic
298 map. This process exposes many edge cases each one is added as a unit test. The paths generated are used to
299 relocate the sensor to the next sampling location, hence experimentally verified to be free of obstacles.

300 *4.2. Automated Data Collection*

301 To obtain an insight into the behavior of Lazy Theta*, it is tested under variable combinations of inputs.
302 The variables that compose the input of the path planner are the starting position, the goal position, the map, the
303 flight corridor width, and the processing time before declaring a path unsolvable.

304 There are some aspects to consider in particular. The length of the final path will be influenced by the
305 distance between the start and the goal as well as by the distribution of obstacles in the environment. The
306 configuration sparse grid must vary as well. The variability involved in generating an octree is tremendous. Each
307 composition of voxel size and quantity has the potential to be an edge case. Setting up a particular configuration
308 of voxels is extremely difficult. To produce the desired octree, it would require manipulating both the content and
309 the order of each point cloud integrated into the map. The flight corridor width determines the number of line of
310 sight checks per node. Increasing the width, while maintaining the maximum amount of time, can be critical in
311 determining whether a path is findable. Finally, the number of seconds the algorithm is allowed to run will also
312 influence the success rate. In this study, sixty seconds was fixed as the maximum amount of time allocated for
313 path generation.

314 To gather information about such diverse factors automated testing was used. Only synthetic maps and
315 experimental snapshots are compatible with this method of testing. In preparation, the map is generated and
316 saved to a file. For each map, several points are identified as informative according to the map's characteristics.
317 The key characteristics of the points are adjacency to openings, proximity to obstacles, and variable distance to
318 other points.

319 The tests adopt the following process: load the map from a file, verify preconditions and then generate the
320 path. As a precondition, no obstacles can exist within the flight corridor width. Each test examines a combination
321 of points that are used interchangeably as start and goal. These sets of tests are repeated to explore different
322 values about the flight corridor width.

323 **5. Results and Discussion**

324 This section begins with a preliminary test of computation time to identify the bottleneck. Different types of
325 maps were used: synthetic, static experimental and continuously generated maps. The second subsection details
326 each dataset and its generation. In the forth subsection, is described the isolated analysis of the different methods
327 of obstacle detection. The fifth subsection, gives a full relation of the findings for each type of map in the HitL
328 environment. Finally, in the sixth subsection are described the results obtained in the outdoor flight experiments
329 where the paths are generated onboard and in real-time.

330 *5.1. Preliminary bottleneck analyses*

331 A preliminary evaluation of computation time reveals that obstacle avoidance is the most critical bottleneck
332 of the algorithm. Table 2 shows which proportion of time obstacle avoidance corresponds to. The information was
333 collected by recording the computational times of LTS_SN on HitL environment using experimental snapshots.
334 Even with different margin values, obstacle avoidance always occupies over ninety-six percent of the total
335 planning time.

336

Table 2. Preliminary inspection of the bottleneck. In this table are shown the computation times involved in generating a path. Firstly is shown the total time used to find a path. The total time can be decomposed in time spent on obstacle detection and the remaining time. The second column details the computational time needed to detect obstacles, both in milliseconds and as a percentage of the total time. In all flight corridor widths, obstacle detection comprises over 96% of the entire time, exposing the bottleneck.

Total computation time for path generation (Milliseconds)	Total computation time used in obstacle detection (Milliseconds)	Flight corridor width (Meters)
5.809.367	5.627.883	2
18.211.941	17.698.871	2,5
37.417.587	36.723.194	3

Figure 2. Octomap of the synthetic scenario: a three-dimensional puzzle. This synthetic map showcases the three-dimensional planning potential of Lazy Theta*. Holes in the obstacles are denoted by letters. The resolution of the map is 0.5 meters such that the smaller cubes have 0.5 meter edges. (a) Front view of the structure. (b) Top-down view of the structure.

337 5.2. Map Generation in the Different Environments

338 This study was conducted using three types of maps: synthetic, experimental snapshots and continuously
339 generated maps⁴.

340 5.2.1. Synthetic map

341 The synthetic map is used in simulation and was developed to showcase the potential of the Lazy Theta*
342 three-dimensional planning. Figure 2 shows a map of this large-scale three-dimensional puzzle. The smaller
343 cubes have a volume of half a cubic meter, the gaps and passages are six meters wide by six meters high. The
344 whole structure measures ninety meters by fifty-six meters and is eighty-five meters tall.

345 The Gazebo simulator emulated the laser measurements used to build the octomap. These measurements
346 were generated with a configuration to match the Hokuyo 10Lx sensor mounted on the UAV platform for the
347 flights. The PX4 simulator is used to emulate the flight of the UAV and the capture of laser measurements. PX4
348 is also the autopilot used in outdoor flights.

⁴ Detailed instructions are available at <https://sites.google.com/view/lazythetastaronline/home>

Figure 3. The UAV used in outdoor flights as seen from above (a) and from the side (b). The platform is a DJI S1000 and consists of one Hokuyo 10Lx sensor (A), an UpBoard with an Intel[®] Atom[™] x5 (B), a 5 GHz wireless communication rocket (C), a pair of batteries (D), a Pixhawk v1 (E), a Here+ RTK (F).

349 5.2.2. Experimental and Continuously Generated Maps

350 Both experimental and continuously generated maps are built with sensor data collected in outdoor flights.
 351 The experimental setup was a Hokuyo 10Lx LIDAR mounted on a DJI S1000 platform flying over an outdoor
 352 scenario with a large obstacle. The onboard processor was the Intel[®] Atom[™] x5 on an UpBoard. The autopilot
 353 running was PX4 running inside a Pixhawk version one. Figure 3 shows the UAV and its parts, whereas Figure 4
 354 depicts the outdoor scenario.

355 During the tests, the start and the goal position, the flight corridor width, and the maximum computation
 356 time were issued from the ground station. The commands passed through 5 GHz wireless communication band
 357 from the laptop to the UAV. Upon receiving the input variables, the UAV used Lazy Theta* to generate a path.
 358 As soon as Lazy Theta* reached a solution, the UAV sent the path back to the ground station through the same
 359 channel.

360 During a mission, the UAV continuously integrates the laser measurements into the map, even during the
 361 path generation. The path is generated directly over the continuously changing octree to avoid the additional
 362 memory needed to create a static copy of the tree. In the target use case of exploration of large environments,
 363 memory shortages could arise from duplicating the map. For the HitL environment, the map is a snapshot taken
 364 from a particular point in the execution. The snapshots enable an extensive analysis of realistic conditions.

365 5.3. Obstacle Avoidance Approaches

366 As previously shown, obstacle detection is the most significant bottleneck in this implementation of Lazy
 367 Theta*. In order to directly measure the impact of the discretization some aspects are considered. First, the
 368 position of the obstacle determines how many rays are needed to find it. Furthermore, the detection stops as soon
 369 as an obstacle is found, making the computational time of generating a path dependent on the configuration of
 370 the terrain. To remove this source of variation, all the rays in the flight corridor are cast. Second, each flight
 371 corridor is sampled a hundred times for each version to remove the influence of memory caching⁵. Finally, in

⁵ The mechanism of storing program instructions and data in closer, faster memory levels.

Figure 4. The outdoor setting for real flights using the UAV in Figure 3, the obstacle to avoid, and the safety pilot.

372 the test two input variables are sampled: the path length and the flight corridor width. Paths varied from six to
 373 forty-seven meters long. The flight corridor widths evaluated were: two, five, and eight meters. The results are
 374 shown in Figure 5 (a) to (c). In a total, a hundred and ninety-two combinations of input were evaluated. The
 375 processing time was measured both with the three and the two-dimensional discretization approaches, the results
 376 are summarized in Figure 5 (d).

377 Among all, the three-dimensional discretization always takes longer on the same path. The total time for each
 378 path generation records that geometrical detection always takes at most half the time of the three-dimensional
 379 discretization. Figure 5 (d) shows all the measurements to the same scale. This graph illustrates how the
 380 computation time scales both regarding the length and the width of the flight corridor. It becomes apparent
 381 that the width has a much more significant impact on the computation time than the length, especially for the
 382 three-dimensional discretization.

383 5.4. Lazy Theta*

384 Three versions of Lazy Theta* were analyzed to evaluate the impact of each contribution on the computation
 385 time. Firstly, LTS version detects obstacles with a three-dimensional discretization of the flight corridor, the
 386 closest to the previous implementation presented in [7]. LTS_SN refers to the version that reduces the number of
 387 neighbors generated but still relies on three-dimensional discretization for obstacle detection. LTS_G version
 388 includes both the reduction of neighbors and two-dimensional discretization.

Table 3. The amount of path generation attempts and the amount that succeeded, for each version, in each map.

	Synthetic			Experimental Snapshots		
	LTS	LTS_SN	LTS_G	LTS	LTS_SN	LTS_G
Path requests	1.118	2.396	2.021	72	72	72
Successful requests	3	700	1.984	14	51	60

389 The diversity of obstacle densities used in the samples is also plotted in Figure 6 (a). It is clear that a
 390 wide variety of densities is inspected in both maps, with the three-dimensional puzzle containing more obstacles
 391 overall. The median of the obstacle density across paths in the maps recorded from experimental data is forty-five
 392 percent. In other words, every time a flight corridor was searched for obstacles, an obstacle was found in forty-five
 393 percent of the rays casted.

394 Figure 6 (b) compares the success rates for the variants with different algorithms, map representation, and
 395 flight corridor widths. This figure highlights that the LTS_G version achieved higher success rates than the other

Figure 5. Obstacle avoidance times for varying flight corridor lengths and widths from experimental data with 0.5 meter resolution. Avoidance time measures the processing time needed to cast all of the rays that cover a flight corridor. Different flight corridor lengths (distance between start and end locations) and widths (safety margin) are shown. (a) The flight corridor measures two meters in width. (b) The flight corridor measures five meters in width. (c) The flight corridor measures eight meters in width. (d) Presentation of the results in the same scale to illustrate the magnitude of the variation in computation time of the two approaches and the influence of the flight corridor width.

396 versions. Figure 6 (b) illustrates the results presented in Table 3. To note that the success rate is higher in the
 397 synthetic map (ninety-eight percent median) than in the experimental snapshots (eighty-three percent median).
 398 Interestingly, using the LTS_G version, the success rate appears to be independent of the width of the flight
 399 corridor.

400 The following sections focus separately on the synthetic map, experimental snapshots, and outdoor flights.

401 5.4.1. Synthetic Map

402 Figure 7 shows an example of a path generated by Lazy Theta*. The path was generated with the LTS_G
 403 version. Qualitatively, the figure illustrates the three-dimensional capabilities of the algorithm. Lazy Theta* can
 404 generate a path that passes through a complex series of openings. The letters have the same correspondence as
 405 seen in Figure 2. In the different perspectives is more explicit that the openings are not aligned along any of the
 406 three axes. Throughout all the path the desired flight corridor width is observed, acting as a safety margin.

407 To show how the three versions fare across a broad range of input sets, Figure 8 portrays the computation
 408 time of various paths with different flight corridor widths. Each of the first three plots is associated with a
 409 particular corridor width, with the data points grouped by version. In all the graphs the points create the shape of
 410 an upward bent cone. The cone has a wider or narrower base depending on the number of ray casts involved.
 411 This shape is explained by the influence of the variability of the configuration of the map on the computation
 412 time. As paths grow longer, there is more space for variability, which results in high variability of computation
 413 time for a given path length.

414 The LTS version is only able to generate a path twice and only for the smaller flight corridor width. In
 415 Figure 8 (a), two lighter blue data points are present for over ten-meter paths. In Figure 8 (b) and (c), no data
 416 point from this version is present at all.

Figure 6. In the synthetic map, the paths generated have a maximum length of a hundred and twenty meters. In the experimental snapshots, the paths have at most thirty-three meters. Both maps have a half a meter resolution. (a) The obstacle density in each map. It registers the relationship between the total number of ray casts and the number of ray casts that detected an obstacle. Unknown space is treated as an obstacle. In each environment, all the individual cases used for data collection are considered. (b) The success rate across versions and maps types. LTS_G has the highest success rate, but LTS_SN already shows improvements in comparison to LTS. Each dot represents the combined success rate of a flight corridor width. The widths sampled were three and nine tenths of a meter, five meters, and five and four tenths of a meter.

Figure 7. Example path (yellow lines) between two points that are 82 meters apart. Purple cubes are voxels whose centers are used as waypoints, and the size of each cube reflects the size of its corresponding voxel. Adequate solution candidates are shown as small green spheres. The white line connects the start (C) and goal (E) positions. The flight corridor is 3.9 meters wide, the map's resolution is 0.5 meters, the gaps and passages are 6 meters wide by 6 meters tall, and the whole structure measures 90 meters by 56 meters and is 85 meters tall. (a) The image shows both the generated path and the world representation. (b) The same path is shown without the occlusion of the world representation. Additionally, the centers of the voxels candidates adequate for the solution are plotted as small green spheres.

417 LTS_G is always faster than LTS and LTS_SN, independently of the width or the length of the flight corridor.
 418 This result validates the hypothesis that discretizing the flight corridor in two dimensions reduces processing time.
 419 In LTS_SN, all three dimensions are discretized and sampled separately. In LTS_G, the points to cast the rays for
 420 the flight corridor are calculated in different coordinate frames. This approach allows for the discretization to be
 421 performed only for the width and the height but not the length. Each ray cast traverses the flight corridor from
 422 the start circle to the farthest point of the end hemisphere.

Figure 8. Computational times needed to find paths using three variants of Lazy Theta* in the simulated puzzle for different flight corridor lengths and widths. The points selected as start and goal were used interchangeably. The computation time need to generate paths that keep a free flight corridor was measure for: (a) a width of 3.9 meters; (b) a width of 5 meters; and (c) a width of 5.4 meters. (d) The results obtained with LTS_G with the three flight corridor widths.

423 In all versions, a broader corridor has less successfully generated paths and the paths that are generated take
 424 longer. This results from the increased number of queries to the map. The discretization step is the same, but a
 425 larger corridor needs to be covered. On the one hand, more queries require more time, on the other hand, a larger
 426 corridor allows for a larger number of possible map configurations.

427 For the LTS_SN version, the effect of the increased number of raycasts in wider corridors is clear. Narrower
 428 corridors allow paths between greater distances to be found. With a width of three and nine tenths meters paths
 429 around a hundred and ten meters are established. Whereas with a five-meter corridor width, the length of the path
 430 does not reach a hundred meters. And with a five and four tenths meter width, the longest path found is eighty
 431 meters.

432 Figure 8 (d) illustrates the effect of the variability of the map. In this graph, only the data points from
 433 LTS_G are plotted. The shapes of the upward bent cone of each corridor overlap each other. However, the cone is
 434 wider for the five and four tenths meter corridor then for a cone with a width of three and nine tenths of a meter.
 435 A broader cone on the horizontal axis is intuitive, as longer paths take more time to generate. A wider cone in
 436 the vertical axis reflects variability in the computation time for the same path length. The variability displayed
 437 is easily explained, the computation time is highly dependent on the underlying configuration of the octomap.
 438 As depicted in Figure 1, the flight corridor volume is covered by multiple rays. The maximum number of rays
 439 is the product of the octomap resolution and the flight corridor width. However, the search ends as soon as an
 440 obstacle is found. Therefore, in Figure 1, the number of rays present corresponds to the worst case scenario
 441 for the obstacle search. Outside this maximum, how many rays are cast depends entirely on the location of the
 442 obstacle within the flight corridor.

443 5.4.2. Experimental Snapshots

444 The computational time of the different Lazy Theta* versions over the experimental snapshots is depicted in
 445 Figure 9. In this setting, the original algorithm (LTS) can only find a significant amount of feasible paths with a

Figure 9. Computation times for different experimental snapshot flight corridors. The same paths are generated with increasing flight corridor widths. (a) Paths calculated with a 3.4 meters flight corridor width. (b) Paths generated with a 5 meters flight corridor width. (c) Paths computed with an 5.4 meters flight corridor width. (d) The impact of the width of the flight corridor for LTS_G.

446 flight corridor width of three meters and nine tenths. In the cases a path is found, it takes much longer compared to either of the other two versions. LTS_SN can handle flight corridors of the same width but as the flight corridor
 447 widens, the path generation starts to fail. In successful cases, the computation time increases dramatically with
 448 the path length. LTS_G is a lot less sensitive to the width of the corridor. In Figure 9 (d), the influence of the
 449 corridor width is compared. Despite the increase in computation time, it is always under three seconds, well
 450 below the set sixty-second limit.
 451

452 5.4.3. Outdoor Flights with a Rotary Wing UAV

453 Results using the LTS approach are not shown because no feasible paths could be generated in this
 454 environment. Figure 10 (a) shows the resulting path received from the UAV using the LTS_SN version to avoid
 455 the obstacle depicted in Figure 10 (b). Here, it is clear that the solution not only avoids the obstacle but also
 456 maintains a safety distance from it along the path.

457 The data points are insufficient to outline a shape in Figure 11. However, as we have previously analyzed a
 458 three-dimensional puzzle in simulation, we can see that the points also fit the shape of an upward bent cone. The
 459 small distance takes very little time to solve. The variability in time increases with the length of the path. The
 460 twenty-meter mark is representative of the impact of map configuration on paths of the same length. For the
 461 same path length, the path generation time varies from ten to over sixty seconds. It is reasonable to assume that
 462 more data would follow this trend

463 6. Conclusions and Future Work

464 This work sets out to qualify Lazy Theta* presented in [7] as a tool in the context of autonomous exploration
 465 of large scenarios. Consequently the path generation must be done in real-time and onboard, further restricting

Figure 10. Photographs from outdoor flights. The UAV avoids an obstacle autonomously (b) that appears green in the map (a) that is generated in real time. In (a), the small cubes' edges are 0.5 meters.

Figure 11. The computation time of the paths generated in real-time, onboard during flight.

466 the computation time. Moreover, the path must always be at a minimum distance to occupied or unknown space.
 467 The associated calculations make obstacle detection the most significant bottleneck.

468 In order to generate paths a hundred times longer than the map resolution within the time frame two
 469 optimizations are introduced. On the one hand, the voxels composing the neighborhood of another voxel are
 470 calculated taking into account the sparse grid that represents the world. In LTS_SN the success rate increases to
 471 consistently over eighty percent. On the other hand, obstacle detection calculations are reduced by restricting the
 472 space discretization of the flight corridor to two dimensions, and bringing the success rate to over ninety percent.
 473 Additionally, the software development methodology adopted is TDD paired with smart monkey testing.

474 Lazy Theta* is able to generate paths both as a local and a global planner. At the local level, the resolution
 475 of the octomap is fine enough to navigate around the obstacle. The paths created can be used directly by the
 476 autopilot. Lazy Theta* can also plan for longer paths at the global planning level. Because of the any-angle
 477 characteristics of Lazy Theta*, the path is smooth enough to avoid a post-processing smoothing algorithm, in the
 478 context of exploration.

479 With LTS_G, the two-phase, geometrical approach to obstacle detection allows the shape of the flight
 480 corridor to be decoupled from its position. The shape can be calculated only once at initialization, and the position
 481 is calculated for each collision check. This highly effective strategy can be applied to many other bottlenecks.
 482 Future work should focus on using it to calculate the information gain of trajectories and points.

483 The contributions keep the deterministic nature of Lazy Theta*. One set of input variables will always
 484 generate the same path. Because the outcome is repeatable, the path planner is uniquely suited for applications
 485 that need to be certified.

486 In the future, the final solution will be further tested outdoors and integrated into an autonomous exploration
 487 architecture. The two-part, geometrical method to analyze space can be used in many ways: to evaluate the
 488 information gain of frontiers, to embed information gain into the heuristics of Lazy Theta* or even to calculate
 489 the observation points of the frontiers according to the sensor.

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502 Abbreviations

503 The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
HitL	Hardware in the Loop
IMU	Inertial measurement unit
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LTS	Lazy Theta* offline version
504 LTS_SN	Lazy Theta* Sparse Neighbors
LTS_G	Lazy Theta* Sparse Neighbors and Geometrical two-dimensional discretization
RRT	Rapidly-Exploring Random Trees
PRM	Probabilistic Road Map
TDD	Test-Driven Development
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle

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620 **Sample Availability:** The files for the octomaps used for data collection are available at the repository of the code https://github.com/margaridaCF/FlyingOctomap_code
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